

Comparing Performance of Freshmen and Sophomores in Mathematics

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Abstract

Two discrete mathematics courses with a significant overlap in contents were taught to freshmen and sophomores. Moreover, these courses differed in their emphasis on mathematical language. We will compare performance of students on comparable problems at the final exam. We focus both on solutions that follow algorithmic procedures and on solutions that require mathematical reasoning.

Introduction

There are many factors that influence learning outcomes of a course. Some of them are related to students:

- their background,
- their mathematical experience, in particular their familiarity with mathematical language,
- their motivation.

These factors are at least as important as the teacher-side considerations like course design, teaching approach and other pedagogical factors.

We used the opportunity to teach two groups that are in a way the exact opposites to compare their performance.

Basic Information on the Courses

We compare two courses on discrete mathematics with a significant subject overlap. For the common topics, these courses had equivalent questions on the final exam.

DMA(E):

- sample size: 32;
- students with one or more year of university experience;
- international students with varying backgrounds;
- exchange students, for many the course was not crucial, hence a lower motivation observed.

DMA:

- sample size: 37;
- recent high-school graduates, having passed a common state-guaranteed exit exam;
- freshmen, their first mathematics course;
- BSc computer science students for whom this course was obligatory for the program.

Results

Both courses included common topics with analogous final exam questions that are being compared here. We did not compare scores, but the actual answers and sorted them into groups. The numbers in tables refer to percentages with respect to the number of final exams written for each course.

Problem: Determine whether the four standard properties (reflexivity, symmetry, antisymmetry, transitivity) are valid for a given binary relation.

Comparison: We focus on the ability to apply a general definition to a particular case (the column “all defs correct” in Table 1 below), and the ability to form concise arguments supporting students' assertions. This can be found as columns “all correct” and “3 or 4 correct”, referring to properties that were handled properly; the latter also includes the previous case (all correct).

Course:	all defs correct	all correct	3 or 4 correct
DMA(E)	88%	18%	52%
DMA	92%	46%	76%

Table 1: Results for problem on properties of relations

Observations:

1. The majority of students knew definitions well. When mistakes were made, they were common to both courses: in reflexivity they felt that an implication should be incorporated in one way or another; and in symmetry they used conjunction in place of implication.
2. The difference in performance was mainly due to the handling of reflexivity. Since this is a straightforward application, the cause of the higher failure rate for DMA(E) is probably general underestimation of this topic.

Problem: Prove an inequality by induction.

Comparison: We focus on how well students handle the difficult task of adjusting induction to an inequality, where a mere substitution of the induction hypothesis does not yield the desired outcome.

Failures were sorted by their cause, in Table 2 we find columns (the numbers in percentages again):

- correct: the proof was correct, perhaps with minor formal errors;
- struct.: structure of induction was wrong;
- backward: backward argument;
- algebra: incorrect handling of inequalities.

Course:	correct	struct.	backward	algebra	other fails
DMA(E)	39%	27%	15%	9%	10%
DMA	38%	13%	22%	27%	0%

Table 2: Results for problem on induction

Observations:

1. The success rate is similar. Students in both groups learned for the first time that induction can be used for other purposes than just proving simple equalities. Interestingly, DMA(E) shows a higher proportion of problems with the structure of the proof. This could be caused by the fact that in the DMA course, the induction was given an extra week of instruction focusing on general structure of induction to alleviate problems observed in previous years. Moreover, while many DMA(E) students claimed to have met induction before, many of DMA students practiced induction in high-school quite extensively, albeit in its weak form.

2. Proving an inequality presents an added challenge in that algebraic operations needed for completing the proof are not all equivalent. This was a bigger challenge for students from the DMA course, in particular they needed to overcome the faulty ``backward proof'' approach which is commonly taught at high schools in the country.

Problem: Solve a given non-homogeneous linear recurrence equation using the standard algorithm, including the undetermined coefficients method.

Comparison: The main focus is not on the result as such, because it is often influenced by numerical errors. Rather, we focus on ability to apply an algorithm that is not one straightforward procedure, but involves several steps, some of which require judgement.

Course:	correct	partially	fail
DMA(E)	52%	30%	18%
DMA	46%	30%	24%

Table 3: Results for problem on linear recurrence

Observations:

1. It seems that freshmen students were somewhat less ready to follow a less trivial procedure.

General conclusions

Typically, going through several mathematical courses at university has a cumulative effect on student's mathematical competencies. We therefore expected the students of the DMA(E) course to do better compared to freshmen, especially in less routine tasks. However, it did not happen, most likely due to difference in motivation.